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The point of view

Key points on writing an effective literature review article: A review of a review

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Abstract: The main goal this point of view, a review of a review is to give directions towards and information on easier article writing, available literature databases, and to address crucial issues during writing, as well as to encourage scientists to write down their ideas, critical opinions, and to document their impression in a specific research field. Literature review usually represents the systematization of a large research data and an evidence overview on the most recent findings in a particular research domain, while in some cases the *magnum opus* of the author's work with the highest impact. An effective scientific literature review can significantly reshape research impact and sometimes can influence clinical decisions. An impactful review article may significantly enhance the visibility and excellence of the researcher's work, and has the power of a lighthouse during a stormy sea of information that is waiting for an experienced guide to arrange research data into the right place for a higher goal.

Introduction

Literature review articles represent the crown of the summary, systematization, and critical overview of the state-of-the-art techniques, approaches, evidence, and findings of a specific research field. An effective scientific literature review article has the strength to shape the perspectives, challenges, and directions in the research topic. The number of published review articles in the field of medical sciences has dramatically increased over the past ten years and has rapidly grown together with knowledge in biology and medicine (1, 2).

Review article types

Pre-writing process of a good-to-great-quality review starts with targeting an issue through defining a **scientific (research) question**. The issue an author wants to elucidate and resolve through the review should be coherent with the current problems of the research field, which should take central place in the manuscript. In practice, it starts with an idea, inspiration, creativity, and eagerness of the author (usually an expert in the field) to share, acquire, systematize, reshape knowledge, and spice it up with potential solutions or directions on how to overcome the problems. The story behind the brilliant idea should be elaborated at the beginning, and ways to overcome a scientific problem should be mentioned throughout the article. The next step usually begins with the choice of the most suitable **review type**. According to readers'/researchers' information requirements, several types of reviews have evolved. In general, the three review article types are the most frequent in the research community-**traditional** or **narrative review**, **systematic review**, and **meta-analysis** (3).

Narrative review is a type of article where knowledge in the field is harmonized into a coherent unit. A traditional review article should be well-framed and shaped in a meaningful story based on up-to-date article information integration. Hierarchically based on evidence importance and impact, it is beneath systematic review and meta-analysis. But this does not mean that it is less worthy and important (4). It may be a good basis for the researchers to systematize their previous findings and compare with recent findings in the field, and to gain new knowledge for planning future research directions. There are some variations on a review article theme, such as **critical review**, **integrative review**, and many others (4).

The core of the **systematic review** is evidence synthesis. Evidence synthesis is a scientific approach that systematically combines findings from previous studies selected by strict criteria. The major goal of the systematic review is to draw broader, panoramic conclusions based on carefully summarized data. The key element is defining precise exclusion and inclusion criteria for the selection of the studies to avoid bias and misinterpretations (5).

Meta-analysis is an approach that statistically analyzes and combines results from more than one study. It is usually used to estimate the precision and effectiveness of the study results, especially when a small sample size is analyzed in an individual study. It is usually interpreted and visualized by a forest plot diagram containing parameters, such as the weight of each included study and confidence interval (6).

Umbrella review is frequently described as a review of other reviews. It is usually written in the form of an overview and synthesis of meta-analyses, systematic reviews, and clinical trials. and based on that, it has the highest ranking not only in "review field", but in the medical field as the

summary of the most relevant and the latest evidence that may be used in clinical practice for decision making (7). A review article should be distinguished from “position statement” (which is more in the form of a guideline), though both use similar approaches in the writing process.

Key steps in writing an effective literature review article

When the topic is clarified and the major research question is defined, the literature should be carefully surveyed and selected. The literature selection process starts with bibliographic database mining. **Keywords** setting and **Medical Subject Headings (MeSH)** proper use are crucial. Choosing inadequate keywords can significantly prolong survey time and deviate from the topic. The most popular electronic **bibliographic databases** are Medical Literature Analysis and Retrieval System Online (MEDLINE), Scopus, Excerpta Medica database (EMBASE), Cochrane Library, Cochrane Register of Trials, Web of Science, etc. (8). PubMed on the other hand is a great search engine with links towards published articles, while PubMedCentral (PMC) is a database of deposited articles (9). It is always a better choice to explore and cross through more than one database when writing a systematic review or meta-analysis. Selection of the literature is based on the authors’ experience and affinities. Some criteria may involve publication date range (for example, last ten or five years); type of the article (for example, to filter only systematic reviews and/or meta-analysis; clinical studies, etc.); type of journal (with specific limited scope, or multidisciplinary); impact of the journal (which is not so relevant criteria, because some great quality articles may be published in lower impact journal and *vice versa*).

The **title** of the review is the first thing that affects and attracts the reader. For the first draft title, keywords may be used. Later, when the manuscript gains its shape and matures, the title can be upgraded into an informative, trendy title, clearly reflecting the topic, focus, issues, and novelty.

The next step should be setting the **structure** of the review. How to describe and summarize what has been found, and then start reading and collecting literature. After the critical assessment of the literature, the most relevant studies should be singled out and described in the text and/or in the tables. Tables should contain parameters relevant to the topic, and studies should be sorted and described accordingly.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria must also be considered (10). After the literature survey, a large number of studies will not meet the criteria for inclusion and will not be acceptable according to the thematically-based parameters previously defined by the authors. If exclusion criteria are set properly, it will significantly speed up the process of omitting ineligible references.

The choice of **methodology** for review writing is also important. It is always a good option to follow the guidelines and flow diagrams when writing a systematic review or a meta-analysis. An example of a great guideline and how to write a systematic review or meta-analysis is “Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA)” which has different flow diagram templates for various review types (11). Some research and academic institutions have paved the path towards easier article review writing by providing a list of frameworks, guidelines, and links to resources with valuable information on how to prepare a systematic review or meta-analysis, followed by a brief description of each article type. In this way, academic and scientific institutions encourage their employees and members of the broader scientific community to

write review articles, and thus increase and improve their writing and scientific/research skills and the impact of their research activities.

Crucial steps for review writing and most frequently used article types are shown in **Figure 1**.

The final part of a good review usually describes perspectives and challenges, and a proposal of the ways to overcome the issue in the scientific field-potential answers to the question from the beginning of the manuscript.

Even the most brilliant scientific thought and idea needs to be put into a frame to be published and easily readable. The recommendation is to target a journal of an adequate scope, even at the beginning, and then to follow the instructions during manuscript writing, which significantly speeds up the process of manuscript submission and changes in word count requirements.

The entire manuscript should fluently follow the narrative. The good quality and effective review should not be repetitive, neither inside the manuscript (repetition segments that are paraphrased from the previous thought) nor outside-to represent the redescription of previous articles. If review article writing has the main purpose to *per se* increase researchers' personal citation index, then it may lead to the overproduction of low-quality review articles.

Perspectives and challenges in “reviewing” (review writing and review reviewing)

The enhanced need for larger data processing and publishing in science and research developed the need for artificial intelligence (AI) based software to assist the entire process. The use of AI-based tools for writing requires good knowledge about all aspects of scientific writing and publishing. AI-based software, besides the writing, may help with title shaping, structure of the manuscript, language assistance, paraphrasing, etc. The most important thing when using these tools is to avoid plagiarism and to leave a personal intellectual mark of the author. Also, if authors decide to use AI-based tools, the journal's requirements and statements should be strictly followed and unequivocally addressed. The greatest challenge in scientific writing and publishing with the assistance of AI may be to estimate the contribution of the author.

On the other hand, besides the role in manuscript creation, use of ChatGPT (OpenAI, San Francisco, California) was discussed and observed in the process of article reviewing by Biswas et al. (12). The authors emphasized that use of ChatGPT may significantly speed up the review process and publication time; avoid bias among report of different reviewers; give linguistic support, and a brief guide on how to improve manuscript (12). The authors also suggest that human involvement in the review process should not be underestimated because AI-based tools because it relies exclusively on available data, which may be unrepresentative, low-scientific-quality, and biased if trained on similar content. The scientist can easily observe these issues and critically analyze the particular situation. The discussion between reviewers and involvement of a person in the reviewing process is crucial because that is how new ideas emerge and how the manuscript quality is significantly improved (12).

Conclusion

An effective and good-quality article should contain an attractive topic, clearly targeted issues in the field, critically analyzed previous research, and a well-organized structure. A good review article should be written in an appropriate scientific manner to attract readers to read further.

Effective review articles significantly increase visibility of the researcher's work and impact on the scientific and broader public. The number of published review articles per researcher tends to increase with time spent in science, and it is always better to be in balance with original research performed or published, which is based on experimental work. If balanced with and based on previous researchers' work, then the strength of the review is higher, as well as the researchers' relevance and competence in the field, then the quality of the review is usually higher. The extensive literature survey results in knowledge expansion and new ideas for future scientific work of junior and senior scientists, as well.

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Contribution

Conceptualization, manuscript and figure design, article writing, editing, and review-Nina Petrović.

Author's Biography

Dr Nina Petrović, PhD is a Research Professor at the Institute for Oncology and Radiology of Serbia (IORS), Belgrade and "VINČA" Institute of Nuclear Sciences-National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia. She gained her MSc in molecular biology (experimental biomedicine) in 2008 and a PhD degree in biology (molecular biology of eukaryotes) in 2014 at Faculty of Biology, University of Belgrade. Dr Petrović's research focus is mainly recognized through the investigation of differential microRNA expression among the groups of breast cancer samples divided according to the invasive potential and how miRNA amounts change over chemo and radiotherapy treatment in association with radiotherapy side effects. Dr Petrović currently investigates differential miRNA/gene/transcriptome/non-coding RNA expression changes and single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) associated with malignant transformation, cancer invasiveness, and response to therapy of breast cancer, prostate cancer, and high-grade gliomas. Since 2017, she has become a part of Radiobiology group at IORS with the main focus on side effects following radiotherapy and biological processes underlying radiotoxicity. During her research career, Dr Petrović formed a new scientific direction in the Republic of Serbia based on the investigation of microRNA level changes during radiotherapy, and association with adverse effects.

Figure 1. Crucial steps and directions towards successful review article writing.

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